

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

TESSE2B is on his way to Barcelona, Spain

Fieldwork has already begun with the boreholes drilling

If you would like to learn more about TESSE2B don't miss the **next workshop and B2B meeting in Barcelona, Spain, at March 2018** and the **TESSE2B Conference in Greece at November 2018**. Stay tuned for more updates!

The house is located in Calonge de Segarra, 100 km from Barcelona.

Four boreholes have already been drilled, each one with 90m depth. Two of the boreholes will be filled with PCM.

You can check the developed work at: [\(link para o video\)](#)

Visit our website and find out more information about this innovative project.

[visit website](#)

TESSE2B pre-prototypes are moving ahead

The Experimental work developed in laboratory, is showing good results and are meeting the intended objectives.

